

Measuring Credit Risk of Bonds Using Expected Default Frequency (EDF) in The KMV-Merton Model with Monte Carlo Simulation

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 09 June 2026	Investment in the capital market is increasingly popular among Indonesians for financial management and achieving financial goals. Bonds, offering fixed income, are a favored instrument but carry credit risk, such as issuer default. The KMV Merton model measures bond credit risk using the Expected Default Frequency (EDF), derived from the distance to default (DD). This model integrates the company's total asset value, equity, and liabilities, providing predictive capabilities. Enhancements to asset value predictions can be made using Monte Carlo simulations, enabling more accurate forecasts across varying scenarios and improving credit risk projections. This study focuses on Sustainable Bonds IV Panin Bank Phase II of 2024, with a face value of IDR 3.91 trillion and a five-year term. A total of 900,000 simulations achieved convergence in the average total asset value with a MAPE of 1.99000456%. The EDF value without asset prediction was 2.84799919E-133 for 2024, while predictions yielded EDFs of 6.33200783E-191 for 2025, 4.45799925E-254 for 2026, and 0.00 for 2027 and 2028. The results showed an almost negligible default risk for all predicted periods, highlighting the robustness of the bond's credit profile.
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KEYWORDS: Bonds, Credit Risk, KMV Merton, Expected Default Frequency (EDF), Monte Carlo Simulation, Probability of Default	

I. INTRODUCTION

The number of investors in the Indonesian capital market reached 13.45 million Single Investor Identifications (SID) as of August 9, 2024, an increase of 1.28 million from the end of 2023 (KSEI, 2024). This indicates a significant upward trend in investment activity in Indonesia. The capital market serves as a platform where parties with surplus funds meet those in need of funds through the trading of securities or financial instruments (Tandelilin, 2017). Bonds are among the most favored financial instruments among investors, as they provide a fixed income in the form of periodic interest payments and principal repayment at maturity. Moreover, bonds are considered relatively safe securities due to their lower issuance costs compared to stocks (Veronica, 2015). However, the benefits of bond investments are inseparable from potential risks. One of the most common risks associated with bond investment is credit risk. Credit risk refers to the risk of loss arising from the bond issuer's failure to fulfill its obligations at maturity. There are two main approaches to credit risk modeling: the structural model and the reduced-form model (Maruddani,

2011). The structural model measures credit risk based on the total asset value of a company, where default occurs when the total asset value falls below the company's liabilities. This model requires information on the dynamics of a firm's total assets, capital structure, debt, and shareholders.

Black & Scholes (1973) initiated the development of structural models through a seminal seminar paper on option pricing. Merton (1974) subsequently expanded and modified this modeling by introducing a framework for corporate bankruptcy, which became relevant for credit risk analysis. As a result, structural models are also known as the Black-Scholes-Merton (BSM) model. This model posits that a company's likelihood of default can be estimated based on indicators such as total assets, equity, and liabilities. When the company's debt increases and the total assets are insufficient to cover it, the company is deemed likely to default. KMV LLC further developed Merton's Model into what is known as the KMV-Merton model. The KMV-Merton model estimates the probability of default through the Expected Default Frequency (EDF), which is derived

from the distance to default (DD), a metric dependent on the market value and volatility of a company's total assets. Monte Carlo simulation can be applied in the KMV-Merton model to account for the uncertainty of future asset values. The model assumes that the value of total assets follows a Geometric Brownian Motion (GBM), whereby asset value uncertainty is captured through the random variation of a standard normally distributed variable Z . The combination of Monte Carlo simulation and GBM enables realistic and dynamic credit risk prediction.

Anggoro et al. (2023), in their study, calculated EDF to measure credit risk using the KMV-Merton model on bonds issued by Bank Mandiri and Bank BRI. The results showed that Bank BRI had a higher probability of default. The present study builds upon this prior research. In addition, another relevant reference is a study conducted by Liu Yan. Yan (2020) applied Monte Carlo simulation to compute the Expected Default Frequency (EDF) under the KMV-Merton model for 90 companies in China, categorized by industry. The study found a significant difference in one of the three categorized groups.

Researchers need to further develop the KMV-Merton model using the Monte Carlo simulation approach to forecast the asset value growth of bond-issuing companies, considering the constantly evolving dynamics of the capital market. Therefore, the objective of this study is to measure the probability of default of corporate bonds in Indonesia using the KMV-Merton model, both with and without asset value forecasting through Monte Carlo simulation. The results of this research are expected to provide a more accurate picture of bond credit risk, thereby assisting investors in understanding the risks and making wiser investment decisions.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A. Material

Bonds are securities that serve as proof of debt issued by a bond issuer and can be traded (Tarmiden, 2015). The bond issuer (also known as the issuer commits to pay interest (coupon) regularly according to an agreed schedule until maturity. In addition, the principal amount of the debt will also be repaid at maturity. However, bond investment also carries the risk of the issuer failing to make payments, either on the coupon or the principal amount, which is known as credit risk. This risk can be estimated using the KMV Merton model. The assumptions of the Merton model used in the KMV Merton framework are as follows (Kulkarni et al., 2005):

The dynamics of the firm's total asset value follow a

$$dV_t = \mu V_t dt + \sigma V_t dW_t \quad (1)$$

stochastic differential equation:

The firm's liabilities consist of a single debt with a face value, so the debt is assumed to be a zero-coupon bond. The

risk-free interest rate is constant. The process of the firm's total asset value follows a Geometric Brownian Motion.

Default can only occur at the time of maturity. There is an absolute priority of claims in the event of default. There are no transaction costs, taxes, or issues related to total asset value. Short selling is allowed at any time.

The normality assumption test of the ln return of total assets is one of the requirements before estimating the volatility of total assets (Asdriago et al., 2012). Ln return of total assets at time t (r_t) has a value of $r_t = \ln R_t = \ln \left(\frac{V_t}{V_{t-1}} \right)$ with a value of R_t is the value of the total asset return at time t , V_t is the total asset value at time t dan V_{t-1} is the total asset value at time $t-1$.

The normality test of the ln return of total assets can be performed using the Jarque-Bera normality test, which aims to measure the difference between the skewness and kurtosis of the sample data to assess whether the data follows a normal distribution or not. The hypothesis formulation for the Jarque-Bera normality test is as follows:

H_0 : The ln return of total assets follows a normal distribution

H_1 : The ln return of total assets does not follow a normal distribution

The significance level used is α with the test criterion is to reject H_0 if $JB > \chi_{\alpha,df}^2$ or jika p-value $< \alpha$. The test statistic used is as follows:

$$JB = \frac{n}{6} \left(S^2 + \frac{(K-3)^2}{4} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $S = \frac{m_3}{m_2^{3/2}}$, $K = \frac{m_4}{m_2^2}$, $m_2 = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n}$, $m_3 = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^3}{n}$, $m_4 = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^4}{n}$

Volatility refers to the magnitude of price fluctuations of total assets (Maruddani, 2011). High volatility indicates that the value of total assets fluctuates within a wide range, while low volatility implies that the value rarely changes and tends to remain constant. The volatility of total assets can be estimated using the standard deviation (Maruddani, 2011). Therefore, the estimation of the volatility of total asset value is as follows:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (r_i - \bar{r})^2} \quad (3)$$

If the total asset values are based on monthly data, then the annual standard deviation (annual volatility) can be estimated as follows:

$$s = \sqrt{12 \left(\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (r_i - \bar{r})^2 \right)} \quad (4)$$

where \bar{r} is a mean of r_t , and n is the number of observations. A stochastic process is a collection of random variables $[X(t), t \in T]$ where t represents time and $X(t)$ represents the state space at time t . At each time t , $X(t)$ has its probability value, with a single value of t from T representing the time index or parameter. One form of a stochastic process is Brownian motion. A stochastic process $\{B_t; t \geq 0\}$ is called Brownian motion if it satisfies the following criteria (Taylor & Karlin, 1998):

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B_t is a continuous function in t .

$B_0=0$ and its increments are continuous.

Every increment B_t-B_s is normally distributed with a mean of 0 and a variance $\sigma^2(t-s)$ for $0 \leq s \leq t \leq T$ or equivalently $B_t-B_s \sim N(0, \sigma^2(t-s))$.

Increments over intervals such as B_s-B_t and B_v-B_u are independent random variables for $0 \leq s \leq t \leq T$ and $0 \leq u \leq v \leq T$.

A stochastic process $\{W_t; t \geq 0\}$ is called a standard Brownian motion if $W_t = \frac{1}{\sigma} B_t$ with the same criteria as B_t , but each increment W_t-W_s is normally distributed with a mean of 0 and a variance $(t-s)$ for $0 \leq a \leq b \leq T$ or equivalently $W_t-W_s \sim N(0, (t-s)) \sim \sqrt{t-s} N(0, 1)$.

Brownian motion with drift μ and variance parameter σ^2 $\{X_t; t \geq 0\}$ is defined by the following linear stochastic differential equation:

$$dX_t = \mu dt + \sigma dW_t \quad ; \mu \in R, \sigma > 0$$

The increment X_t-X_s for $0 \leq s \leq t \leq T$, is given by:

$$X_t - X_s = \mu(t-s) + \sigma(W_t - W_s)$$

$$X_t = X_s + \mu(t-s) + \sigma(W_t - W_s) \quad (5)$$

$W_t - W_s \sim N(0, (t-s))$. If we apply the transformation $Z = \frac{W_t - W_s}{\sqrt{t-s}}$, then $Z \sim N(0, 1)$. Therefore, $W_t - W_s = Z\sqrt{t-s}$ where Z is a random sample from the standard normal distribution. Based on the definition of Brownian motion, $X_t - X_s \sim N(\mu(t-s), \sigma^2(t-s))$ and the increments are independent.

Geometric Brownian Motion with drift parameter μ and a variance σ^2 $\{S_t; t \geq 0\}$ is defined by the following stochastic differential equation:

$$dS_t = \mu S_t dt + \sigma S_t dW_t \quad ; \mu \in R, \sigma > 0$$

The increment $\ln(S_t) - \ln(S_s)$ for $0 \leq s \leq t \leq T$, is given by:

$$\ln(S_t) - \ln(S_s) = \ln\left(\frac{S_t}{S_s}\right) = \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)(t-s) + \sigma(W_t - W_s)$$

$$S_t = S_s \exp\left\{\left(\mu - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)(t-s) + \sigma Z\sqrt{t-s}\right\} \quad (6)$$

Based on the definition of Brownian motion, each increment of the value $\ln(S_t) - \ln(S_s) = \ln\left(\frac{S_t}{S_s}\right) \sim N\left(\left(\mu - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)(t-s), \sigma^2(t-s)\right)$ so $\frac{S_t}{S_s} \sim \text{LOGN}\left(\mu, \sigma^2\right)$ with $\mu_t = \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)(t-s)$ and $\sigma_t^2 = \sigma^2(t-s)$.

Based on Equation 1 and the similar solution in Equation 6, the value of total assets, assuming it follows Geometric Brownian Motion in the future, can be estimated using the following equation:

$$V_t = V_s \exp\left\{\left(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)(T-t) + \sigma Z\sqrt{T-t}\right\} \quad (7)$$

where V_T is the value of the company's total assets at time T , V_t is the value of the company's total assets at time t , r is the drift or risk-free interest rate, σ is the volatility of V_t , W_t is the Standard Wiener Process (standard Brownian motion with mean 0 and variance 1), $T-t$ (τ) is the time distance between T and t , and Z is a number or random sample distributed according to the standard normal distribution.

Equity in the Merton model is a call option on the company's asset value, with the bond's principal value K (liabilities) as the strike price or exercise price. A detailed explanation can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Equity or Call Option at Maturity

Condition	Total Assets	Bond (Liabilities)	Equity
No Default	$V_T \geq K$	K	$V_T - K$
Default	$V_T < K$	V_T	0

Source: Merton (1974)

Thus, the general formulation of equity value in the Merton model is:

$$E_T = \begin{cases} V_T - K, & \text{if } V_T \geq K \\ 0, & \text{if } V_T < K \end{cases}$$

or it can also be written as:

$$E_T = \max[V_T - K, 0] \quad (8)$$

The present value of the company's equity with debt (face value) K is given by Equation 9.

$$E_{\text{merton}} = \exp(-r\tau) E[\max[V_T - K, 0]] \quad (9)$$

The solution for the equity formulation is:

$$E_{\text{merton}} = V_t \Phi(d_1) - K \exp(-r(T-t)) \Phi(d_2) \quad (10)$$

$$d_1 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{V_t}{K}\right) + \left(r + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)(T-t)}{\sigma\sqrt{(T-t)}}, \quad d_2 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{V_t}{K}\right) + \left(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)(T-t)}{\sigma\sqrt{(T-t)}} = d_1 - \sigma\sqrt{(T-t)}$$

where K represents the face value of the bond, r is the risk-free interest rate, $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution.

Liabilities are obligations held by a company sourced from external funds, such as bank loans, bond issuances, and other sources. The amount of liabilities can be formulated as follows:

$$L(V_t, \tau) = V_t - E(V_t, t) \quad (11)$$

where $L(V_t, \tau)$ represents the company's liability (debt) at time τ and $E(V_t, t)$ represents the company's equity value at time t .

The KMV model (Kealhofer McQuown Vasicek) calculates the Expected Default Frequency (EDF) as a probability of default over the coming years. Default or failure to pay occurs when the total asset value of the company at maturity is less than the debt or face value (Asdriargo et al., 2012). Crosbie & Bohn (2003) mentioned three main steps in determining the probability of default in the KMV Merton model, which are:

Estimating the total asset value and volatility.

Calculating the Distance to Default (DD).

Calculating EDF using the DD value.

The formulations for calculating EDF and DD are as follows:

$$EDF = \Phi[-d_2] = \Phi[-DD] = \Phi\left[-\frac{\ln\left(\frac{V_t}{K}\right) + \left(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)(T-t)}{\sigma\sqrt{(T-t)}}\right] \quad (12)$$

Monte Carlo simulation, also known as Sampling Simulation, is a method used to repeatedly evaluate a deterministic model that involves generating random

numbers as one of the inputs. Monte Carlo simulation uses stochastic models to produce better results for real-world experimental research (Syam et al., 2018). The Monte Carlo simulation procedure provides a probability density through random number generation and is closely related to the Law of Large Numbers to obtain the average value as an estimator of the expected value of a random variable (Kwok, 2000). In other words, after repeating the simulation a sufficient number of times (N), the expected value (E) is obtained by calculating the sample mean (\bar{X}) of the estimates generated in the simulation sample (Kwok, 2000). It is necessary to discretize the asset value estimation model in Equation 7 to convert the continuous model into a form that can be computed at specific time steps, such as daily, monthly, or yearly intervals. The discretization process is carried out by dividing time into small intervals Δt so that the GBM equation becomes:

$$V_{t+\Delta t} = V_t \exp \left\{ \left(r - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) \Delta t + \sigma Z \sqrt{\Delta t} \right\} \quad (13)$$

where:

$$E[V_{t+\Delta t}] = V_t \exp(r\Delta t) \quad (14)$$

Based on Equation 13, by generating random numbers Z_i as many as N times for each time step, the Monte Carlo simulation GBM equation to calculate the total asset value at time $V_{t+\Delta t}$ for each simulation path i becomes:

$$V_{t+\Delta t}^{(i)} = V_t \exp \left\{ \left(r - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) \Delta t + \sigma Z_i \sqrt{\Delta t} \right\}; i=1, 2, \dots, N \quad (15)$$

Therefore, after running N simulations, the average value of the simulation results is:

$$\bar{V}_{t+\Delta t} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N V_{t+\Delta t}^{(i)}$$

Based on the Law of Large Numbers concept, when the number of simulations N approaches infinity, the average value of the Monte Carlo simulation becomes an estimate of the expected value of the total assets, as follows:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \bar{V}_{t+\Delta t} \approx E[V_{t+\Delta t}] = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N V_{t+\Delta t}^{(i)} \approx V_t \exp(r\Delta t) \quad (16)$$

The Law of Large Numbers ensures that the estimate from the Monte Carlo estimator converges to its analytical solution as the number of samples increases (Glasserman, 2013).

MAPE is a standard measure used to assess the evaluation, accuracy, or precision of a prediction model, expressed as the average percentage of actual values. The MAPE equation is (Makridakis et al., 1982):

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{A_t - F_t}{A_t} \right| \times 100\% \quad (17)$$

where n is the total number of data points observed, A_t is the actual value at time t , and F_t is the predicted value at time t .

B. Method

The bond data used is a type of corporate banking bond listed on PT Kustodian Sentral Efek Indonesia (KSEI). The bond used is coded PNB04CN2 with a Pefindo rating of

idAAA. The risk-free interest rate in this study is the BI rate data from November 2024, which is 6% per year. The company's liabilities are assumed to consist only of a single debt with a face value, so bond interest/coupon rates will not be used (zero-coupon bonds). The monthly data for the company's total assets to be used spans the period from November 2019 to October 2024, totaling 60 data points. In the analysis for total asset prediction, the total asset data is divided into two sets: 80% training data (48 data points from November 2019 to October 2023) and 20% testing data (12 data points from November 2023 to October 2024).

According to KSEI (2024), the bond in this study is the Continuous Bond IV Panin Bank Phase II of 2024, with a face value of IDR 3,910,000,000,000, issued on October 9, 2024, and maturing on October 8, 2024. This study uses R-Studio and Microsoft Excel software. The steps for analysis are as follows:

1. Determine the bond data and monthly total asset data from the issuing company.
2. Perform calculations without predicting the total asset.
 - a. Calculate descriptive statistics of the total asset data.
 - b. Conduct a normality test on the ln return of the total asset data using the Jarque-Bera test.
 - c. Calculate the volatility by estimating the standard deviation of the ln return of the total asset data.
 - d. Determine the risk-free interest rate using the BI rate data.
 - e. Calculate the equity and liability values.
 - f. Calculate the Distance to Default (DD) value.
 - g. Calculate the probability of default using the Expected Default Frequency (EDF) value in the KMV Merton model.
3. Perform calculations with predicted total assets using a Monte Carlo simulation.
 - a. Split the total asset data into training data (80%) and testing data (20%).
 - b. Calculate descriptive statistics for the total asset training data.
 - c. Conduct a normality test on the ln return of the total asset training data using the Jarque-Bera test.
 - d. Calculate the volatility of the ln return of the total asset training data.
 - e. Determine the risk-free interest rate using the BI rate data.
 - f. Predict the total asset value for future periods V_T until maturity using the Geometric Brownian Motion (GBM) model with N Monte Carlo simulations. The initial value V_t is taken from the last total asset data point in the training set.
 - g. Calculate the average total asset from all simulations and periods to ensure convergence of results. If the results converge, stop the simulation as the predicted total asset has been achieved.
 - h. Calculate the predicted total asset results using the average of the N Monte Carlo simulations that have converged for each period.

- i. Calculate the model prediction evaluation using the MAPE value.
 - j. Determine the prediction time points from the predicted total asset values for each year. These predicted total asset values will be used in the KMV Merton model.
 - k. Calculate the equity and liability values from the predicted total asset for each prediction point at every year until maturity.
 - l. Calculate the Distance to Default (DD) for each prediction point at each year until at least one year before maturity.
 - m. Calculate the probability of default using the Expected Default Frequency (EDF) value in the KMV Merton model for each prediction point at each year until at least one year before maturity.
4. Summarize the predicted total asset results using the Geometric Brownian Motion (GBM) model with a Monte Carlo simulation.
 5. Interpret the results of the development of total asset values, equity, and liability, both without and with predicted total assets, using the GBM model with Monte Carlo simulation.
 6. Interpret the results of the development of Expected Default Frequency (EDF) both without and with predicted total assets using the GBM model with Monte Carlo simulation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the descriptive analysis of the ln return of total asset data produce an average value (0.00128718), standard deviation (0.02244689), and annual volatility (0.07775832) for the data without total asset predictions. Meanwhile, the results of the descriptive analysis of the ln return of total asset data produce an average value (-0.00047784), standard deviation (0.02074622), and annual volatility (0.07186702) for the data with total asset predictions. The normality assumption test of the ln return data using the Jarque-Bera test produces the following conclusions:

H_0 : The ln return of total assets (without prediction) & training (with prediction)

The Bank Pan Indonesia data is normally distributed

H_1 : The ln return of total assets (without prediction) & training (with prediction)

The Bank Pan Indonesia data is not normally distributed. Using a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and the test statistic from Equation 2, the values listed in Table 2 are obtained.

The conclusion based on Table 2 shows that H_0 is accepted because $JB(0.4985 \ \& \ 0.6925) < \chi^2(5.9915)$ and $p\text{-value}(0.7794 \ \& \ 0.7074) > \alpha(0.05)$ indicating that the log returns of total asset data (without prediction) and training data (with prediction) for Bank Pan Indonesia are normally distributed.

Table 2. Summary of the Ln Return Data Total Asset Test Statistics

Value	Without Prediction	With Prediction
Skewness (S)	-0.0453	-0.0430
Kurtosis (K)	3.4411	3.5884
Chi-Square hitung (JB)	0.4985	0.6925
P-Value	0.7794	0.7074
Alpha	0.05	0.05
Chi-Square tabel ($\chi^2_{\alpha=0.05;df=2}$)	5.9915	5.9915

Source: Processed from research results

The prediction of total asset values using a Monte Carlo simulation generates as many expected values as possible to show convergence towards a certain value. The prediction period for the total asset values is 72 months, from November 2023 to October 2029. This period is based on the length of the testing data period up to the bond maturity date. The data for Bank Pan Indonesia's total assets is recorded monthly, so $\Delta t = \frac{1}{12}$. Then, to predict for 72 months, the value of $t + \Delta t$ will reach $t + \frac{72}{12}$ or $\Delta t = 6$ years. Therefore, the model for predicting the first step ($k=1$) in November 2023 ($t + \frac{1}{12}$) will use the total asset value of October 2023 as V_t which is formulated as follows:

$$V_{t+\frac{1}{12}}^{(i)} = 189974404000000 \exp \left\{ \left(0.06 - \frac{1}{2}(0.07186702)^2 \right) \left(\frac{1}{12} \right) + 0.07186702 Z_i \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{12} \right)} \right\}$$

Thus, the model for predicting the k step in general is:

$$V_{t+\frac{k}{12}}^{(i)} = V_{t+\frac{(k-1)}{12}} \exp \left\{ \left(0.06 - \frac{1}{2}(0.07186702)^2 \right) \left(\frac{1}{12} \right) + 0.07186702 Z_i \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{12} \right)} \right\}$$

The simulation will be performed as many times as possible and will stop when the average total assets from all simulations and all periods show a convergent value, limited to four decimal places. Additionally, the value *set.seed* (2020 + k) will be used for each k -th step as a form of replication. The simulation results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Statistical Summary of Ln Return Test in the Study

No	Number of Simulations	Average Total Assets from All Simulations and All Periods
1.	10	2.2023E+14
2.	100	2.2725E+14
3.	1,000	2.2887E+14
4.	10,000	2.2879E+14
5.	100,000	2.2935E+14
6.	500,000	2.2928E+14
7.	800,000	2.2923E+14
8.	900,000	2.2923E+14

Source: Processed from research results

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The results in Table 3 show convergence at the seventh result ($N=800,000$) and the eighth result ($N=900,000$) with a value of $2.2923E+14$. The convergence of the average total asset values in each simulation is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Convergence Graph of Total Asset Values (Source: Research analysis results using R-Studio)

The proof for Equation 16 is as follows:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow 900,000} \frac{1}{900,000} \sum_{i=1}^{900,000} V_{t+\Delta t}^{(i)} \approx 189,974,404,000,000 \exp(0.06 \times \Delta t)$$

where: $\Delta t = \frac{k}{12}; k=1,2,3,\dots,72$. If $a = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N V_{t+\Delta t}^{(i)}$ and

$$b = V_t \exp(r\Delta t).$$

Table 4. Proof of Convergence Results Based on the Comparison of Empirical Average with Theoretical Average of Prediction Results and Testing Data

Δt	Date	a (Empirical Average)	b (Theoretical Average)	Testing Data
1/1	01/11/2023	190,930,313,933,164	190,926,654,662,802	187,943,590,000,000
2/1	01/12/2023	191,892,588,603,948	191,883,678,501,915	198,845,169,000,000
3/1	01/01/2024	192,858,488,103,924	192,845,499,442,985	189,020,325,000,000
5/1	01/03/2024	194,796,062,105,363	194,783,628,933,817	199,210,202,000,000
6/1	01/04/2024	195,773,373,946,519	195,759,985,936,917	197,584,461,000,000
7/1	01/05/2024	196,751,226,094,723	196,741,236,949,862	200,851,882,000,000
8/1	01/06/2024	197,736,779,321,510	197,727,406,503,978	196,688,687,000,000
9/1	01/07/2024	198,729,755,627,609	198,718,519,253,554	200,073,846,000,000
10/12	01/08/2024	199,725,418,051,419	199,714,599,976,462	203,174,651,000,000
11/12	01/09/2024	200,724,235,310,582	200,715,673,574,771	207,914,763,000,000
12/12	01/10/2024	201,728,624,501,713	201,721,765,075,373	209,618,957,000,000
...	-
70/12	01/08/2029	269,536,960,189,262	269,586,511,779,745	-
71/12	01/09/2029	270,878,104,	270,937,819	-

12	2029	156,643	,793,454	
72/12	01/10/2029	272,230,423,488,613	272,295,901,266,770	-
Average		229,228,573,845,596 ≈ 2.2923E+14	229,242,979,202,734 ≈ 2.2924E+14	-

Source: Processed from research results

Based on Table 4, the result of the empirical average (Monte Carlo simulation conducted 900,000 times) showed values that approach the theoretical average (expected value). Therefore, a simulation of 900,000 iterations will be used to predict the total asset values for each month over the next 72 months. The calculation of the MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error) will be based on the testing data for the company's total assets, as shown in Table 4. The calculation is according to Equation 17 as follows:

$$MAPE = \left(\frac{1}{12} \sum_{t=1}^{12} \left| \frac{187,943,590,000,000 - 190,930,313,933,164}{187,943,590,000,000} \right| + \left| \frac{209,618,957,000,000 - 201,728,624,501,713}{209,618,957,000,000} \right| \right) \times 100\%$$

$$MAPE = \left(\frac{0.23880055}{12} \right) \times 100\% = 0.0199000456 \times 100\% = 1.99000456\%$$

The MAPE value of 1.99000456% indicates that the prediction model used in this study provides highly accurate predictions.

In this study, to obtain the default risk of Bank Pan Indonesia using the predicted total asset values, a selection of prediction points will be made as reference points. For each year up to the bond maturity date, one prediction point will be chosen, which is the month of October. The reason for selecting October is that the Sustainable Bond IV of Bank Panin, Phase II 2024 matures in October. This is done to simplify the time steps because it results in τ having a rounded difference from the maturity date. The predicted development of equity and liability values for the KMV Merton model is as follows:

Table 5. Prediction Results of Total Asset, Equity, and Liability Values

Date (as of Oct)	Data Note	Predicted Total Assets (V_t)	Equity Value (E_t)	Liability Value (L_t)
2024	Actual	206,722,357,757,134	209,618,957,000,000	2,896,599,242,866
2025	Prediction	214,178,146,053,005	211,102,431,116,235	3,075,714,936,770
2026	Prediction	227,435,105,795,207	224,169,199,268,589	3,265,906,526,618
2027	Prediction	241,484,654,287,582	238,016,795,380,018	3,467,858,907,564
2028	Prediction	256,408,660,256,222	252,726,360,929,907	3,682,299,326,314
2029	Prediction	272,230,423,488,613	268,320,423,488,613	3,910,000,000,000

Source: Processed from research results

The Expected Default Frequency (EDF) results between the use of total asset data without prediction (actual) and the total asset data from the Geometric Brownian Motion (GBM) using Monte Carlo simulation are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. EDF Values Without and With Total Asset Prediction

Date (as of Oct)	Data Note	T-t	Predicted Total Assets (V_t)	DD	EDF
2024	Actual	5	206,722,357,757,134	24.5388	2.84799919E-133
2025	Prediction	4	214,178,146,053,005	29.4498	6.33200783E-191
2026	Prediction	3	227,435,105,795,207	34.0269	4.45799925E-254
2027	Prediction	2	241,484,654,287,582	41.6991	0.00000000E+000
2028	Prediction	1	256,408,660,256,222	59.0069	0.00000000E+000

Source: Processed from research results

The EDF value at the bond maturity date cannot be estimated because the total asset value at that time is already known with certainty (not a probability), so whether the company defaults or not will be determined exactly by whether the total asset value is less than or greater than its liability. Based on Table 5, it is found that the predicted total asset value at the maturity date in October 2029 is greater than its liability ($V_T(272,230,423,488,613) \geq K(3,910,000,000,000)$) so it can be confirmed that the company will not default on its bond. Therefore, the EDF estimation will be conducted at least one year before the maturity date, which is October 2028.

Table 6 shows that the Expected Default Frequency (EDF) value is very small, both for the result using data without prediction (actual) and for the predicted total asset data. This indicates that Bank Pan Indonesia has almost no risk of default on the Sustainable Bond IV Bank Panin Phase II Year 2024, with a value of IDR 3.91 trillion at all predicted time points. Therefore, the bond can be considered safe to purchase if there are investors interested, as the company is in a very healthy financial condition to repay its debt over the bond period.

The prediction of the company's total assets using a Monte Carlo simulation can be conducted to provide a more dynamic illustration of the possible development of the company's total assets and liabilities in the future.

IV. CONCLUSION

The measurement of bond credit risk using the KMV Merton model to determine the probability of corporate default can provide an overview of the potential risks or benefits of an investment decision. Investing in bonds often requires forecasting a key variable that is directly related to the risk, namely, the company's total assets. This is necessary to understand the future development or prospects of the company as a form of anticipation against potential risks. Therefore, this study also employs total asset prediction using the Geometric Brownian Motion (GBM) model with Monte Carlo simulation to forecast the development of possible credit risk under the KMV Merton model.

Based on the results of the analysis presented in the Results and Discussion section above, the total asset prediction using the GBM model with Monte Carlo simulation for Bank Pan Indonesia resulted in 900,000 simulations to achieve convergence in the average simulated total asset value, with a MAPE of 1.99000456%. Furthermore, the measurement of Expected Default Frequency (EDF) without total asset prediction (actual data) for the Sustainable Bond IV Bank Panin Phase II Year 2024 resulted in a value of 2.84799919E-133 for the year 2024. Meanwhile, the EDF values using predicted total assets were 6.33200783E-191 for 2025, 4.45799925E-254 for 2026, and 0.00 for 2027 and 2028. The predicted development of Expected Default Frequency (EDF) shows decreasing values at each prediction point throughout the bond's active period. The results indicate that the estimated risk of credit default on the company's bond is extremely low, suggesting that the company has virtually no risk of default on the Sustainable Bond IV Bank Panin Phase II Year 2024 at any point within the bond's active period. These findings can serve as a basis for decision-making for investors interested in investing in bonds.

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